

Interview with Keita Kanazashi, Taiko Performer

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Today, we are pleased to present on CoolJapan.es the interview granted to us by Mr Keita Kanazashi on the occasion of his attendance at the II Bilbao Manga Convention, where we attended as guests and took part in various activities.

Keita Kanazashi, born in Tokyo, is a taiko performer, specialising in the traditional Japanese drum —which has various forms, all of which Kanazashi masters. He began his journey as a musician at a very young age, during his primary school years. Since then, he has performed on this instrument at numerous festivals and ceremonies throughout Japan.

Kanazashi during one of his taiko performances at the Bilbao Manga Convention

Furthermore, he has collaborated in various concerts with renowned artists such as singer Hiroshi Itsuki and musician Shinnai Nakasaburo, who was proclaimed a National Treasure in Japan. He has participated in significant projects promoting taiko and other Asian instruments, as well as events like the international MUSIC FOR WATER tour held in France. He is also remembered for being part of the group Seiwa Taiko, contributing his talent alongside them.

But he has not limited himself to taiko alone, as Kanazashi has created his own projects in which he designed and set up his own stage. He also works with artists from both the West and the East, and has training in dance under the master Eisuke Hanayagi. He has collaborated with kabuki artists such as Tazaemon Mochizuki, reflecting his interest in the performing arts.

Interview with Keita Kanazashi

Cool Japan: Most taiko performers start practising and preparing from a very young age. Could you tell us a little about how you began?

Keita Kanazashi: I started playing the taiko when I was ten years old. At that time, there was a matsuri, a festival, near my home, and it seemed very spectacular and impressive. In fact, I did not think from the beginning that I would become a professional. Just attending these festivals, and a little encouraged by my parents, they told me, “Well, if you want, you can start playing.”

When I was nineteen, I felt a desire to pursue musical performance. I have two siblings, and at that time we were asked if we would be interested in forming a taiko group together. It was after this, at the age of twenty-one, that my two brothers and I formed a taiko group, composed of three members. And it was not that we followed a particular master; instead, we learned from those people, from our predecessors, whom we admired. We learned different styles, both the *ohayashi* of kabuki theatre and Japanese dance —*nihon buyō*— attempting to express, through the taiko, sounds that are typically Japanese.

Kanazashi demonstrating his skill with wind instruments as well, not just percussion like the taiko

Later, at the age of twenty-four, we embarked on our first tour abroad, and when I was twenty-six, we also visited Africa to give a performance and showcase the taiko. Currently, I am in Spain [as of 2016], but I am also conducting various international tours to demonstrate the appeal of a traditional Japanese instrument such as the wadaiko.

Cool Japan: Could you tell us a little about the origin of the taiko in Japanese mythology?

Keita Kanazashi: Well, I think there are different theories regarding the origins of this instrument. Some say it originated in Africa and travelled to Asia via the Silk Road, reaching Japan through Okinawa. There are also theories stating that it already existed in ancient times, from the Jōmon period in Japan [Late Palaeolithic].

As for the taiko in Japan... studying its origins, it is difficult to determine the exact beginnings and development of the instrument, but it is certain that the taiko has evolved in Japan since ancient times. From very early on, playing this instrument in its primitive form helped it develop within Japan, given that Japan is an island nation.

All this contributed to the development of a unique taiko culture. In fact, the wadaiko is precisely an instrument that appears in Japanese mythology. It features in the story of the goddess Amaterasu, who represents the Sun. She is said to be the creator of Japan and the world, and once hid herself inside a cave, causing the Sun to disappear. The people of the Earth sought a way to bring her out. It was a woman who began to dance and, through the sound of instruments such as the Japanese drum—the wadaiko or taiko—they drew her attention, prompting the concerned people to play the instrument as well.

Seeing how captivating and lively the sound was, Amaterasu emerged, causing the Sun to reappear in the world. Therefore, it is an instrument that appears in Japanese mythology and has been present for the Japanese people since antiquity. In fact, this also partially reflects the origins of the arts in Japan in a mythological sense. If you are curious to learn more about this story, which is later reflected in Japanese arts, you can look up two works: *Ame no Uzume no Mikoto* and *Ama no Iwato*. These works convey this spirit very well.

Certainly, some of these stories have subsequently influenced other narratives reflected in animation.

Cool Japan: For people who have never heard of the taiko or of you, what can you tell them about the experience of hearing it for the first time or attending one of your performances?

Keita Kanazashi: Surely, when people hear the taiko, they will think it is a traditional and ancient instrument. However, the type of drum I play and perform with is somewhat more contemporary. In fact, there are different types of settings in which the wadaiko serves its purpose.

Not only in kabuki theatre is the taiko featured, but also in folk and popular performances, and even in modern shows, where it can serve as background music for a song. There are therefore many contexts in which this instrument can be played.

Even so, the taiko, with its distinctive, deeper sound compared to other instruments, and as its sound is transmitted through air vibrations, allows listeners to feel the sound emanating from the taiko in their bodies. Therefore, I believe it is an instrument everyone can enjoy without overthinking. Simply by feeling it in their own body.

It is said that the sound of the taiko is similar to that of a human heartbeat, and that it resembles the sound we hear when we are still in our mother's womb. So, even if you are not Japanese, I believe it is a sound that resonates with anyone, allowing them to feel and enjoy it. I strive to convey this feeling so that it can be perceived by all.

Cool Japan: Finally, in light of what you have just said, could you tell us the cultural message you hope your work conveys to both foreign and Japanese audiences?

Keita Kanazashi: Indeed, on stage, I would like people not only to witness and absorb the performance, but also to appreciate the cultural aspect, just as I did yesterday during my performance [referring here to the concert given the day before this interview]. I hope that people are encouraged not only to learn about the taiko, but also to understand, through it, some of the essence and characteristics of Japanese culture. This is something I wish to continue doing from now on.

And just as the taiko, the Japanese drum, was historically an instrument that connected people—used, for example, in medieval Japan to transmit messages over long distances, or in shrines and temples as a vehicle to convey something, a message to the gods—I would like the taiko to be an instrument that connects people today who are interested in Japan, much like fans of manga and anime become curious about Japan through a shared interest in these works.

I also see how people develop an interest in Japan through its cuisine. I would like people, through the taiko or groups like Seiwa Taiko, who promote this instrument, to see it as a vehicle for connecting with others who share an interest in wadaiko and Japan.

I hope to continue working, to return once more to the Basque Country and perform the taiko again, to see you all, and for you to enjoy this art and my music. See you again!

Kanazashi, both focused and completely joyful, conveying unforgettable sensations to the audience through his music

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Sources

- **Interview conducted by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es] and Juan Carlos Pérez Izquierdo [CoolJapan.es] | **Interview interpreted by:** Hajime Kishi
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